

PREDICTION OF PRECIPITATION BY DEVELOPING GROWTH MODEL FOR YAVATMAL STATION

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to development of growth model of prediction of precipitation by development of logistic growth model for Yavatmal station. Daily rainfall data of 38 years (1981 to 2018) were collected from Maharain and NASA websites, then transformed and used for probability analysis by Weibull's method. The Logistic model was developed after finding the location specific constants and weekly cumulative precipitation values were predicted. The values of weekly cumulative precipitation at 25, 50 and 75% were 1287.74, 730.73 and 370.15mm respectively. The values of predicted weekly cumulative precipitation at 25, 50 and 75% were 1048.51, 610.91 and 314.39 mm respectively. The Logistic model gave reliable prediction at 50% probability levels when compared with actual data. It can be used for rainfall prediction while irrigation and crop planning. Also the validation of Logistic model was done by using two statistical parameters as coefficient of determination and percent average absolute deviation. The model was tested with observed precipitation for the period from 2019-2023 at probability level of 25, 50, and 75%. The cumulative predicted value at 50% probability levels was 610.91 mm and the average observed value for subsequent five years (2019-2023) was 1160.00 mm.

Key words: Precipitation, Weibull method, logistic model, prediction

Introduction

Globally, rainfed agriculture accounts for 80% of total cultivated area and produces 60% of the world's food (Rockström *et al.*, 2007). India ranks first among the countries that practice rainfed agriculture both in terms of extent (86 Mha) and value of production (Sharma *et al.*, 2010). Overall precipitation plays important roles in agricultural production. But rainfall varies unevenly over period and distance. Increased climate variability has made rainfall patterns more inconsistent and unpredictable (Kumar *et al.*, 2005). Both of these things have been made the unavailability of rainwater during crucial period of cropping seasons.

To face such challenge of cropping in uncertain precipitation conditions there is need of proper crop planning to decide the time of sowing, type of crop depending upon the available soil moisture and rainwater and requirement of any protective irrigation. It will off course depend on how much precipitation and evapotranspiration occur in the same week. Therefore, information about the probability of rainfall in specific weeks is needed in order to calculate the amount of water will be available during the relevant weeks through precipitation which can be predicted by statistical growth model of precipitation prediction.

Rainfall prediction or precipitation prediction refers to the process of using various scientific techniques to estimate the amount of rainfall that is expected to occur in a particular location over a certain period of time (Sarah Benziane, 2024). There are different methods for prediction of precipitation, one of such method is statistical models (Ashby *et al.*, 2005). These models use historical weather data to predict future weather patterns (Glahn, 2019).

Growth models, such as exponential growth, logistic growth, or polynomial growth, fall under the broader category of statistical models (Feller 1968). Growth model refers to a mathematical or statistical framework used to simulate and predict the growth or development of precipitation over time. These models state the complex processes involved in the formation and distribution of precipitation in a given region for particular duration (Chow, 1988).

Out of different growth models logistic model is preferred in hydrology and meteorology for prediction of precipitation. It is a mathematical equation derived from the logistic growth function, which describes the sigmoidal (S-shaped) growth pattern. In the context of precipitation, the logistic model is adapted to represent the cumulative distribution of precipitation over a specified period (McMahon *et al.*, 2003, Hossain *et al.*, 2004 & Kumar *et al.*, 2012). These models are location specific, meaning thereby the constants in these models vary from region to region depending on the rainfall pattern and it predict

the rainfall up to satisfactory level of accuracy if properly developed (Tiwari and Singh, 1985).

Methodology

The Yavatmal district of Central Vidarbha Zone of Maharashtra state is located between 20.39925° of North latitude while 78.11792° of Eastern longitude. The district comes under assured rainfall area of VIII Agroclimatic Zone with average annual rainfall of 1050 mm mostly received during June to September months from the north-eastern monsoon rains. To improve the accuracy, the data were collected from different sources was as Maharain website (<https://maharain.maharashtra.gov.in/>) and NASA website (<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>) of Yavatmal district and compared with each other. The daily precipitation data was transformed into corresponding 52 standard meteorological weeks (SMW). But for current study the data of only 22nd to 43rd SMW were taken for further analysis.

To find predicted values of precipitation by logistic model first there is need to find the location specific constant of this model. Which is calculated from probability analysis of SMWs. Probability analysis was done by using Weibull (1939) formula for each SMW. The rainfall values were plotted against corresponding computed probability on normal probability paper and for all these weeks the precipitation probability curves were drawn.

$$P_p = \frac{m}{n+1} \times 100$$

Where,

P_p = plotting position percent chance

m = rank number when the data are arranged in descending order of magnitude with highest value marked as 1 and

n = total number of years for which the data are available

The cumulative precipitation was computed for each week for 25, 50 and 75% probability levels.

Next step in model development is calculation of constants. The cumulative rainfall values were chronologically divided into three equal segments. The subtotal of reciprocals of individual observation in each of these segments was obtained. The subtotals were represented in chronological order by S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . The difference between the subtotals i.e. S_2-S_1 and S_3-S_2 were represented by d_1 and d_2 respectively. Number of observations in each segment is denoted by 'n' (Mhaske *et al.*, 2011).

The values of constants a, b and c of this model were computed by the relationship given by Mills (1995) as given below:

$$a = \frac{1}{n} \left(S_1 - \frac{d_1}{c^{n-1}} \right)$$

$$b = \left(\frac{d_1(c-1)}{(c^n-1)^2} \right)$$

$$c = \left(\frac{d_2}{d_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

After finding constants, Logistic model was found at 25, 50 and 75% probability, which is expressed as bellow:

$$\frac{1}{Y} = a + bc^X$$

Where,

Y = predicted cumulative precipitation (mm)

X = standard week starting from 1 to 22 for meteorological week from 22 to 43

a, b, and c = constants

The mathematical expression for prediction of cumulative precipitation were developed using growth model and cumulative precipitation at all probability level were predicted. It is essential to validate model for its reliability in prediction and to select that model for agro climatic condition suitable for choosing right model from different level of probabilities. For suitability of Logistic model was checked by using two statistical parameters as coefficient of determination and percent average absolute deviation (Mhaske *et al.*, 2012).

Coefficient of determination (R^2) is calculated from the square of coefficient of co-relation (R) is given by:

$$R = \frac{\sum XY - \left(\frac{\sum X \sum Y}{n} \right)}{\sqrt{(\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{n})(\sum Y^2 - \frac{(\sum Y)^2}{n})}}$$

Where,

R = Co-efficient of co-relation

$\sum X$ = Sum of the observed cumulative precipitation

$\sum Y$ = Sum of the predicted cumulative precipitation

$\sum XY$ = Sum of the product of corresponding observed and predicted cumulative precipitation.

$\sum X^2$ = Sum of square of observed cumulative precipitation.

$\sum Y^2$ = Sum of the square of predicted cumulative precipitation.

n = no. of reading

The percent average absolute deviations between observed values of cumulative precipitation and corresponding predicted value cumulative precipitation are calculated given by:

$$d = \frac{Y - \bar{Y}}{Y} \times 100$$

Where,

Y = Observed values of cumulative precipitation

\bar{Y} = Corresponding predicted values of cumulative precipitation

Using the above equation values of co-efficient of correlation, coefficient of determination and percent average absolute deviation for

each week were calculated for at 25, 50 and 75% probability levels.

For testing of model values for subsequent five years to be compared with predicted values. Average values of 5 years were taken and it were compared with the predicted value of selected probability level.

Results And Discussion

Average weekly precipitation corresponding to each standard week at probability levels at 25, 50 and 75% worked out using Weibull's method from the 22nd met. week to 43rd met. week. Calculated values are given in table 1. These average weekly precipitation values are then converted into weekly cumulative precipitation value and are given in table 2 at different probability levels. Table 2 shows that, the weekly cumulative precipitation at 50% probability level of Yavatmal station is showing closer fit with the weekly average cumulative precipitation of 857.73 mm upto 43rd met. week. So that model appears reliable at 50% probability level for Yavatmal station for prediction.

The cumulative precipitation at 25% and 75% probability level is showing values with greater difference and lower difference respectively, than the weekly average cumulative precipitation. Hence prediction at 25% and 75% probability levels do not provide reliable prediction. The values of constants for Logistic model were developed using the method suggested by Mills (1955) from the previous 38 years precipitation data and are given in the table 3.

By using this constant logistic model is developed at different probability levels. Using the Logistic model developed for Yavatmal station the cumulative rainfall values were predicted for all the weeks and at different probability levels of 25, 50 and 75% and are presented in table 4. It is observed from the table that, when prediction values at 25%, 50% and 75% are compared with weekly average cumulative precipitation, the prediction values at 25% are higher and values at 75% are lower than the average precipitation of Yavatmal station. While the prediction at 50% probability was showing closer fit with the observed values of precipitation of the same station. Similar model was developed by Mhaske *et al.* (2010) for monthly prediction.

The suitability of logistic model developed and tested by computing two statistical parameters called coefficient of determination and percent average absolute deviation is shown in the table 5. From the table it is observed that the Logistic model gave the reliable prediction at 50% probability level and hence it can be suitably used for prediction of precipitation in these areas for crop planning and water management by developing the logistic model with prediction at 50% probability.

The comparison of predicted values of precipitation at 50% probability level was made with average actual precipitation from 1981 to 2018 at Yavatmal station and thereafter average observed values of Yavatmal station of weekly precipitation from 2019 to 2023 were compared with weekly precipitation values at 50% probability level and presented graphically in figure 2. Which show good fitting between predicted and actual average values. Similar prediction was made by Sulochana and Shrinivasan (2011) and Mhaske *et al.* (2015). The careful observation of the figure 2 shows that there is closed fitting between predicted values and average observed values.

Table 1. Average weekly precipitation at different probability levels for Yavatmal station

Met. weeks	Dates	Weekly precipitation at different probabilities (mm)		
		25%	50%	75%
22	28-3 June	7.84	3.61	0.81
23	4-10 June	33.64	19.35	7.84
24	11-17 June	51.84	33.64	17.64
25	18-24 June	67.24	38.44	19.36
26	25-1 July	72.25	46.24	27.04
27	2-8 July	81.00	47.61	25.00
28	9-15 July	90.25	56.25	33.64
29	16-22 July	92.16	60.84	36.00
30	23-29 July	94.09	60.84	33.64

31	30-5 Aug	96.04	57.76	27.04
32	6-12 Aug	77.44	49.00	27.04
33	13-19 Aug	70.56	40.96	21.16
34	20-26 Aug	75.69	40.96	20.25
35	27-2 Sept	67.24	37.21	17.64
36	3-9 Sept	68.89	37.21	18.49
37	10-16 Sept	51.84	26.01	10.24
38	17-23 Sept	50.41	26.01	12.96
39	24-30 Sept	43.56	18.49	7.29
40	1-7 Oct	43.56	17.64	6.25
41	8-14 Oct	31.36	8.41	0.81
42	15-21 Oct	16.00	4.00	0.01
43	22-28 Oct	4.84	0.25	0.00

Table 2. Weekly cumulative precipitation at different probability levels for Yavatmal station

Met. weeks	Dates	Weekly cumulative precipitation at different probabilities (mm)			Weekly average cumulative precipitation from year 1981 to 2018
		25%	50%	75%	
22	28-3 June	7.84	3.61	0.81	4.50
23	4-10 June	41.48	22.96	8.65	26.09
24	11-17 June	93.32	56.60	26.29	72.96
25	18-24 June	160.56	95.04	45.65	116.20
26	25-1 July	232.81	141.28	72.69	173.95
27	2-8 July	313.81	188.89	97.69	229.18
28	9-15 July	404.06	245.14	131.33	289.86
29	16-22 July	496.22	305.98	167.33	356.12
30	23-29 July	590.31	366.82	200.97	420.70
31	30-5 Aug	686.35	424.58	228.01	486.02
32	6-12 Aug	763.79	473.58	255.05	543.89
33	13-19 Aug	834.35	514.54	276.21	583.31
34	20-26 Aug	910.04	555.50	296.46	631.76
35	27-2 Sept	977.28	592.71	314.10	673.90
36	3-9 Sept	1046.17	629.92	332.59	717.63
37	10-16 Sept	1098.01	655.93	342.83	753.64
38	17-23 Sept	1148.42	681.94	355.79	786.11
39	24-30 Sept	1191.98	700.43	363.08	806.98
40	1-7 Oct	1235.54	718.07	369.33	830.42
41	8-14 Oct	1266.90	726.48	370.14	844.15
42	15-21 Oct	1282.90	730.48	370.15	853.55
43	22-28 Oct	1287.74	730.73	370.15	857.73

Table 3. Values of constants for logistic model at different probability levels for Yavatmal station

Model	constants	Values of constants at different probability levels		
		25%	50%	75%
Logistic Model	a	0.0010	0.0016	0.0032
	b	0.0763	0.1666	0.7564
	c	0.5640	0.5349	0.4698

Table 4. Predicted weekly cumulative precipitation using logistic model for Yavatmal station at different probability levels compared with mean observed values

Met. weeks	Dates	Predicted weekly cumulative precipitation at different probabilities (mm)			Mean observed values
		25%	50%	75%	

22	28-3 June	22.73	11.02	2.79	4.50
23	4-10 June	39.63	20.28	5.88	26.09
24	11-17 June	68.26	36.84	12.25	72.96
25	18-24 June	115.23	65.44	24.98	116.20
26	25-1 July	188.30	111.92	48.80	173.95
27	2-8 July	293.17	180.47	88.38	229.18
28	9-15 July	427.42	268.43	142.82	289.86
29	16-22 July	576.26	363.10	200.96	356.12
30	23-29 July	717.12	447.54	248.50	420.70
31	30-5 Aug	831.80	511.12	279.57	486.02
32	6-12 Aug	914.27	553.17	297.01	543.89
33	13-19 Aug	968.42	578.63	305.98	583.31
34	20-26 Aug	1001.89	593.23	310.39	631.76
35	27-2 Sept	1021.81	601.35	312.50	673.90
36	3-9 Sept	1033.40	605.79	313.50	717.63
37	10-16 Sept	1040.06	608.19	313.98	753.64
38	17-23 Sept	1043.85	609.48	314.20	786.11
39	24-30 Sept	1046.00	610.17	314.31	806.98
40	1-7 Oct	1047.21	610.55	314.35	830.42
41	8-14 Oct	1047.90	610.74	314.38	844.15
42	15-21 Oct	1048.29	610.85	314.39	853.55
43	22-28 Oct	1048.51	610.91	314.39	857.73

Table 5. Values of coefficient of determination and percent average absolute deviation between predicted cumulative precipitation and their observed values using Logistic model for Yavatmal Station

Model	Coefficient of determination and percent absolute deviation at different probability level					
	25%		50%		75%	
	Coefficient of determination	Percent absolute deviation	Coefficient of determination	Percent absolute deviation	Coefficient of determination	Percent absolute deviation
Logistic model	0.9281	22.15	0.9354	23.39	0.9329	28.38

Figure 1. Comparison of predicted and observed values at 50% probability level by Logistic model for Yavatmal station

Comparison between predicted values at 50% probability level and observed values for subsequent 5 years

Figure 2. Comparison between cumulative observed precipitation for subsequent 5 years and predicted values at 50% probability level by Logistic model

Table 6. Comparison of predicted and observed of subsequent five years (2019-2023) at 50% probability level for Yavatmal station

Met. weeks	Dates	Cumulative observed value (Average of 5 years in mm)	Predicted values
22	28-3 June	12.23	11.02
23	4-10 June	31.68	20.28
24	11-17 June	77.57	36.84
25	18-24 June	108.63	65.44
26	25-1 July	154.11	111.92
27	2-8 July	235.32	180.47
28	9-15 July	341.73	268.43
29	16-22 July	443.59	363.10
30	23-29 July	527.29	447.54
31	30-5 Aug	578.69	511.12
32	6-12 Aug	629.53	553.17
33	13-19 Aug	691.10	578.63
34	20-26 Aug	711.13	593.23
35	27-2 Sept	742.54	601.35
36	3-9 Sept	806.45	605.79
37	10-16 Sept	856.17	608.19
38	17-23 Sept	896.47	609.48
39	24-30 Sept	942.24	610.17
40	1-7 Oct	956.36	610.55
41	8-14 Oct	974.33	610.74
42	15-21 Oct	994.54	610.85
43	22-28 Oct	1001.72	610.91

Conclusions

From the study, it can be concluded that Logistic growth models can be developed by using historical daily rainfall data for Yavatmal station. Location specific Logistic model is more suitable for prediction of precipitation after evaluation of statistical parameters. Therefore, Logistic model gives reliable prediction of precipitation at 50% probability levels and hence, it can be suitably used for prediction of precipitation in Yavatmal areas while planning irrigation water, crop planning, and designing the soil and water conservation structures.

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